

Lipoprotein Phospholipase A2 as a Potent Marker of Atherosclerosis and Cardiovascular Risk Assessment in Patients with Rheumatoid ArthritisGeorge CVS¹, Krishnan J², Harine SS³, Babu TG⁴¹Resident, Department of General Medicine, Government Medical College Thrissur, India²Professor, Department of General Medicine, Government Medical College Thrissur, India³Medical Student, Department of General Medicine, Government Medical College Thrissur, India⁴HOD, Department of Radiology, Government Medical College Thrissur, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Introduction:** The two diseases atherosclerosis and Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA) are considered to share many similarities, Patients with RA have increased atherosclerosis compared with normal individuals.**Aim:** To study if lipoprotein phospholipase A2 can be a potent marker of atherosclerosis in RA patients and Correlate lipoprotein phospholipase A2 (Lp-PLA2) levels with the carotid intimal thickening to predict risk of atherosclerosis events in RA patients.**Methods:** A Case control study conducted among 100 patients came to < study site is not mentioned due to blinded review > in 1 year period. Patients with serologically confirmed RA was taken as cases and Age and sex matched inpatients with other minor ailments without RA are taken as controls included. Cardiovascular events with or without RA patients were excluded. After taking consent, data collected by self-made questionnaire, entered in SPSS and analysed by frequencies, percentages, chi square, t value and Mann Whitney U test wherever applicable.**Results:** The mean age 54.7 ± 9.82 , majority were female (88%). Case and controls were matched for age, sex and comorbidities. There was statistically significant higher level of low- density lipoprotein in cases 121 ± 25.48 compared to control 104.92 ± 22.62 . Similarly, an increased level of Lp-PLA2 was found in RA patients with a mean value around 134.22 ± 37.86 .**Conclusion:** CVD risk is enhanced by having RA. This study was statistically proven by increased Lp-PLA2 which was proven by increased Carotid intima media thickness in RA patients.**Keywords:** Rheumatoid arthritis; atherosclerosis; lipoprotein; lipoprotein-associated phospholipase A2.

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Introduction

Atherosclerosis is currently recognized as an inflammatory disease per se, [1] Atherosclerosis and Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA) are considered to share too many similarities, even though the link between them is yet, not evident [2]. Patients with RA have increased atherosclerosis compared with the normal individuals. Co-morbidities in chronic inflammatory diseases are now considered matter of major concern as they represent a major cause of morbidity and lead to an increased mortality of the patients with these conditions.

With respect to this, RA is a chronic inflammatory disease associated with high risk of cardiovascular events due to accelerated atherosclerosis [3]. However, traditional cardiovascular risk factors remain important the accurate estimation of cardiovascular risk among RA patients remains an area of active investigation [4]. There are risk scoring systems like QRISK 3 (QRESEARCH Cardiovascular risk algorithm) which calculate the ten-year mortality risk

due to cardiovascular disorders in RA patients. Data from several literature demonstrate that risk factors account for only a portion of the overall risk for cerebrovascular disease in RA patients with the additional risk attributed to inflammation [5]. Lipoprotein-associated phospholipase A2 (Lp-PLA2) is a member of the phospholipase A2 superfamily, a family of enzymes that hydrolyze phospholipids. Epidemiological data have consistently demonstrated the association of increased levels of Lp-PLA2 with increased risk of coronary heart disease [6].

In the circulation, Lp-PLA2 is carried bound mainly to LDL, and several epidemiological studies in the normal individuals have shown a correlation between Lp-PLA2 levels and traditional cardiovascular risk factors [7]. In the general population, higher concentrations of Lp-PLA2 have also been shown to be associated with an increased risk of cardiovascular diseases (CVD) [7]. Previous studies of patients with thalassemia, metabolic syndrome, or HIV

infection, each diagnosis being characterized by an increased inflammation, have shown an association between Lp-PLA2 and subclinical atherosclerosis measured by intima media thickness [8]. Increased carotid media intima thickening is regarded as an early indicator of a generalized atherosclerosis [9]. Several studies in the normal individuals, as well as in patients with RA, have shown a relationship between an increased intima media thickness and a future cardiovascular event [10].

We, and others, have previously shown that patients with established RA have a premature atherosclerosis as measured by an increased intima media thickness of the common carotid artery compared with controls [11]. Our objective is to enlighten the association of lipoprotein phospholipase a2 as a potent marker of atherosclerotic inflammation which will reliably identify atherosclerosis in RA patients. It may be an important therapeutic target and may have an important role in prevention, risk stratification and targeted treatment. It will also earmark a new consideration to modify the cardiovascular risk stratification in RA patients. The present study aimed to evaluate if lipoprotein phospholipase a2 (Lp-PLA2) can be a potent marker of atherosclerosis in Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA) patients. Moreover, to see the correlation of lipoprotein phospholipase a2 (Lp-PLA2) levels with the carotid intimal thickening to predict risk of atherosclerosis events in RA patients.

Methods

Study setting and Population: A case control study was conducted in the General Medicine Department, < study site is not mentioned due to blinded review > for a period of one year. All patients with serologically confirmed RA patients taken as cases, Age, and sex matched inpatients with other minor ailments without RA are taken as controls are included in the study. Cardiovascular diseases with RA patients and who are not willing to participate in the study were excluded. This study was approved by the institutional review board.

Sample size: Sample size is calculated using the formula of two means estimating the difference of two means– finite population correction. In a study by Anna Sodergren et al. [12] positive correlation was observed between Lp-PLA2, and atherosclerosis as compared to age and sex matched controls. Similarly, lipoprotein phospholipase a2 levels correlated with the carotid intimal thickening.

Standard deviation of cases= 38.9, Standard deviation of controls = 41.7

Estimated difference between means =6.5

Desired confidence level (1- α) % = 99

Population size =50, required sample size = 46

Sample size formula (n) = $z^2 \cdot 1 - \alpha / 2 \cdot [2S^2 p] / d^2$

$s_2p = SD$ in the cases + SD in the controls / 2, the

sample size adjusted for finite population, $N_{FINITE} = F \cdot X_n$

Where, $F = 1/1+n/N$

s_2p = pooled standard deviation, d = precision, α = significance level, N = population size.

Study procedure: After taking an informed consent all patients satisfying the inclusion criteria were enrolled into the study. All the patient's demographic data, risk factors for atherosclerosis comorbid conditions like Diabetes Mellitus, Hypertension, smoking, alcohol, and family h/o vascular events considered along with history of vascular events. Height, weight, BMI, Pulse rate, Blood pressure, was also recorded RA factor, anti CCP, routine investigations (Haemoglobin, renal function test, serum electrolytes), CDAI (Clinical Disease Activity Index) score for disease activity, lipid profile, QRISK 3 score taken to predict the risk of atherosclerosis in RA patients.

Carotid USG done to measure intima media thickness to prove the evidence of atherosclerosis by measuring internal carotid artery of both sides and the average value is taken for comparison between groups. A fasting venous sample collected to estimate level of lipoprotein pla2 and processed via photometry method. Duration of statin therapy also considered. After selection of cases, age and gender matched controls recruited from non-rheumatoid subjects as inpatients for other ailments. Detailed history, screening with USG carotid, Demographic data, routine investigations, lipid profile, lipoprotein pla2 sample taken for comparison.

Study tools: 1. Questionnaire 2. CDAI score 3. QRISK 3 score 4. Lab investigations 5. USG Carotid.

Statistical analysis: Data analysed by using statistics (SPSS) version 25. Continuous variables expressed as mean with standard deviation (SD) or as median with IQR. Categorical variables expressed as frequencies and percentages. The risk factor profile between cases and controls were compared using chi square test. Lipoprotein phospholipase a2 levels between two groups were compared by using student's test or Mann Whitney U test as per data distribution.

Results

In present study, Table 1 presented that, out of 50 participants in case group, 6 (12.0%) were male and 44 (88.0%) were female. Whereas in control group 6 (12.0%) were male and 44 (88.0%) were female. The p value showed that sex is comparable between groups ($p=1.000$). Out of 50, nearly 26 (52.0%) participants had comorbidity in case group and 25 (50.0%) participants had comorbidity in control group. The p value showed that the status of comorbidity was comparable between groups ($p=0.841$). Out of 50 nearly 3 (6.0%) of participants were smokers in case group and 2 (4.0%) were smokers in

control group. The distribution of smoking status was statistically not associated with groups ($p=1.000$). Out of 50 nearly 3 (6.0%) of participants were used statin in case group and 2 (4.0%) were used in control group. The p value showed that statin use was comparable between groups ($p=1.000$).

In the present study Table 2 shows that, the mean age was 54.70 ± 9.82 in case group and 54.70 ± 9.82 in control group. The p value showed that age was comparable between groups ($p=1.000$). The mean body mass index was 22.73 ± 3.88 in case group and 21.93 ± 2.40 in control group. The p value showed that body mass index and groups were statistically not significant ($p=0.215$). The mean low-density lipoprotein value was significantly higher in case group 121.40 ± 25.48 compared to 104.92 ± 22.26 in control group ($p=0.001$). The mean high-density lipoprotein value was 49.98 ± 9.92 in case group and 47.26 ± 9.71 in control group. It is statistically not significant ($p=0.169$). The mean total cholesterol value was significantly higher in case group 197.72 ± 36.17 compared to 181.38 ± 25.88 in control group ($p=0.011$). The mean Triglycerides value was 135.62 ± 47.31 in case group and 127.84 ± 33.07 in control group. It is statistically not significant ($p=0.343$). The mean lipoprotein phospholipase A2 value was significantly higher in case group 134.22

± 37.86 compared to 106.48 ± 28.39 in control group ($p<0.001$). The mean CIMT value was significantly higher in case group (0.68 ± 0.16) compared to control group (0.54 ± 0.14). In Table 3, the mean QRISK 3 score was 8.91 ± 8.17 in case group and 6.81 ± 6.88 in control group. It is statistically not significant ($p=0.090$). In table 4, the mean high-density lipoprotein value was significantly higher in Monoclonal antibody cases 57.30 ± 12.33 compared to MAB absent cases 48.15 ± 8.44 . The mean lipoprotein phospholipase A2 value was significantly lower in monoclonal antibody cases 102.40 ± 31.46 compared to MAB absent cases 142.18 ± 35.52 . The CIMT value was significantly CIMT in monoclonal antibody cases 0.77 ± 0.21 compared to MAB absent cases 0.65 ± 0.14 . The mean high-density lipoprotein value was significantly lower in CRP positive cases 46.45 ± 10.24 compared to CRP negative cases 52.75 ± 8.88 . The study variables LDL, LPPA2, CIMT and QRISK 3 score was statistically not significant. In table 5, Out of 50 participants in the study group, 10 (20.0%) participants MAB was present. In Table 6 out of 50 nearly 24 (48.0%) study subjects had remission, 14 (28.0%) had low activity, 9 (18.0%) had moderate activity and 3 (6.0%) had high activity. The mean CDAI value was 7.87 ± 11.95 .

Table 1: Comparison of variables between groups

Variables	Groups		χ^2 Value	p Value
	Case (n=50)	Control (n=50)		
Sex				
Male	6 (12)	6 (12)	0	1
Female	44 (88)	44 (88)		
Comorbidity				
Yes	26 (52)	25 (50)	0.04	0.841
No	24 (48)	25 (50)		
Smoking				
Yes	3 (6)	2 (4)	0	1
No	47 (94)	48 (96)		
Statin Use				
Yes	3 (6)	2 (4)	0	1
No	47 (94)	48 (96)		
Data presented as n (%).				

Table 2: Comparison of variables between mean groups

Parameters	Group (N=50)		t value	p value
	Case	Control		
Age	54.7 (9.82)	54.7 (9.82)	0	1
BMI	22.73 (3.88)	21.93 (2.40)	1.248	0.215
LDL	121.4 (25.48)	104.92 (22.26)	3.445	0.001
HDL	49.98 (9.92)	47.26 (9.71)	1.386	0.169
Total cholesterol	197.72 (36.17)	181.38 (25.88)	2.598	0.011
Triglycerides	135.62 (47.31)	127.84 (33.07)	0.953	0.343
Lipoprotein phospholipase A2	134.22 (37.86)	106.48 (28.39)	4.145	<0.001
CIMT	0.68 (0.16)	0.54 (0.14)	4.548	<0.001
Data presented as mean (SD). BMI, body mass index; CIMT, carotid intima media thickness; HDL, high density lipoprotein; LDL, low density lipoprotein.				

Table 3: Comparison of QRISK 3 score between groups

Groups	QRISK 3	Mann Whitney U value	p value
Case	8.91 (8.17)	104	0.09
Control	6.81 (6.88)		
Data presented as mean (SD).			

Table 4: Comparison of study variables with MAB - rituximab

Variables	MAB		t Value	P Value
	Yes (n=10)	No (n=40)		
LDL	133.2 (18.84)	118.45 (26.25)	1.667	0.102
HDL	57.3 (12.33)	48.15 (8.44)	2.784	0.008
LPPLA2	102.4 (31.46)	142.18 (35.32)	3.248	0.002
CIMT	0.77 (0.21)	0.65 (0.14)	2.137	0.038
QRISK 3	11.56 (10.03)	8.25 (7.64)	1.151	0.255
Comparison of study variables with CRP				
Variables	CRP		t Value	p Value
	Positive (n=22)	Negative (n=28)		
LDL	124.64 (17.81)	118.86 (30.26)	0.793	0.432
HDL	46.45 (10.24)	52.75 (8.88)	2.326	0.024
LPPLA2	133.14 (40.7)	135.07 (36.21)	0.178	0.86
CIMT	0.66 (0.19)	0.69 (0.14)	0.477	0.635
QRISK 3	7.07 (6.36)	10.35 (9.21)	1.426	0.16
Data presented as mean (SD). CIMT, carotid intima media thickness; HDL, high density lipoprotein; LDL, low density lipoprotein; LPPLA2, lipoprotein-associated phospholipase A2; QRISK 3, cardiovascular risk score.				

Table 5: Distribution of MAB of study participants

MAB	Number of patients (N=50)
Yes	10 (20)
No	40 (80)
Data presented as n (%). MAB, Monoclonal antibodies	

Table 6: Distribution CDAI of study participants

CDAI	Number of patients (N=50)
Remission	24 (48)
Low activity	14 (48)
Moderate activity	9 (18)
High activity	3 (6)
Data presented as n (%). CDAI, clinical disease activity index.	

Discussion

Study comprised of 50 seropositive RA patients and 50 age and sex matched controls. The predominant study population was female 88% each in case and control with mean age of 54.70±9.82. Associated comorbid conditions were present 52 % cases and 50% controls, 6% of cases and 4% of control groups were smokers and statin users which was statistically not significant. A study by Anna Sodergren et al. out of 40 controls 80% were women and out of 71 RA patients 86% women were included. In this the mean age (SD) of the RA patients was 51.5 years, while that of the controls was 48.1 years. Out of 35 (58%) of the RA patients and out of 14 (39%) of the controls admitted to having smoked at some point in the past.

Out of 5 (12%) controls and 6 (9%) RA patients have ever taken statins [12]. Lipid profile in both groups were compared, RA group had higher LDL mean of

121.04 ± 25.48, Total cholesterol 197.2 ± 36.17. The patients with RA have shown an atherogenic lipid profile. The United Sanitary Institutions of Pecs, Hungary et al conducted a study on lipid profile of RA patients which had a similar increase in LDL and Total cholesterol levels [13]. LpPLA2 was significantly higher in RA patients, mean value 134.22 ± 37.86 and it prospectively correlated with increased CIMT in patient group (0.68±0.16). In a similar study by Anna Sodergren et al where study subjects were followed up for 5 years the mean LpPLA2 was 144 and CIMT 0.52 mm at onset and 0.58mm at 5 years [12]. Patrick H Dessein et al study has taken RA Patients with an IMT > or = 0.60 mm and plaque were considered to have atherosclerosis and advanced atherosclerosis, respectively [13].

The mean disease duration in the current study was 9.62 ± 6.66 years and methotrexate duration of 7.99 ± 5.26 years. Association between disease duration,

CIMT and LpPLA2 was attempted but was found to be statistically insignificant, no association could be found with methotrexate duration and atherosclerosis markers. Out of 10 (20.0%) participants were treated with MAB i.e., Rituximab. The mean high-density lipoprotein (HDL) value was significantly higher in MAB treated cases 57.30 ± 12.33 compared to cases who have not received MAB 48.15 ± 8.44 .

The mean LpPLA2 value was significantly lower in MAB treated cases 102.40 ± 31.46 compared to cases who have not received the treatment 142.18 ± 35.52 . The CIMT value was significantly higher in MAB cases 0.77 ± 0.21 . This could be indicative about the high disease activity these patients had and the relative protective effect monoclonal antibody offers in atherosclerosis. Diana S Novikova et al, proves that RA patients without a history of cardiovascular disease, rituximab therapy effectively reduces systemic inflammation, improves lipid profile, atherogenicity index, and improves elastic characteristics of the artery wall [14].

The disease activity of RA patients was measured with CDAI, out of 24 (48.0%) had remission, 14 (28.0%) had low activity, 9 (18.0%) had moderate activity and 3 (6.0%) had high activity. The current study mean CDAI value was 7.87 ± 11.95 . The given scores clearly indicate most of the RA patients were in near complete remission, this could have decreased the risk of atherosclerosis in the present group.

D H Solomon et al study discovered a substantial trend towards a decreased risk of cardiovascular events with improved disease activity among a large cohort of RA patients followed for a median of 2.7 years: a 21% reduction in cardiovascular risk for each 10 points lower CDAI and a 53% reduction from high disease activity to remission [15]. Carlos Gonzalez et al study [16] CIMT was greater in RA patients who experienced cardiovascular events (1.01 ± 0.16 mm) compared with the remaining RA patients who did not have cardiovascular complications (0.74 ± 0.12 mm) but the study group were predominantly associated with hypertension, diabetes mellitus and dyslipidaemia which would have further contributed to the atherogenic process. A comparison was done between both cases and control group to predict the ten-year risk of cardiovascular events by using QRISK3 score as it had inclusion of Indian ethnicity and rheumatoid arthritis in its variables. The mean QRISK 3 score was 8.91 ± 8.17 in case group and 6.81 ± 6.88 in control group. It is statistically not significant ($p=0.090$), hence this over the fact that existing scoring systems underrate the risk of cardiovascular disorders in RA patients. It provides scope for development of newer scoring systems to predict cardiovascular events in RA group.

A large cohort and longer duration would have given greater reliability to the present study. A serial monitoring of parameters would have strengthened the correlation between lipoprotein phospholipase A2 (LpPLA2) and carotid intima media thickness to predict atherosclerosis EULAR suggested scoring system like m SCORE could not be applied to Indian ethnicity, hence limited the statistical analysis of scoring systems in this study.

In the present study, CIMT measurements of sub-clinical atherosclerosis among Rheumatoid Arthritis patients showed a correlation with Lipoprotein phospholipase A2 levels. The scope of LpPLA2 to predict subclinical atherosclerosis is evident, hence can be considered as a marker of atherosclerosis which can be a predictor of future cardiovascular disorders.

Though CIMT was not in a high-risk for cardiovascular disease prediction, heterogenicity and a trend towards higher range was there. The higher disease remission rate would have contributed to relatively lower CIMT.

The need for inclusion of markers of subclinical atherosclerosis (LpPLA2) into the existent cardiovascular risk scores is emphasized. Use of rituximab (MAB) has proven protective, by reduced LpPLA2 level and high HDL but it did not affect the carotid intima media thickness.

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